

The Effect of Leadership and Competence on Employee Performance with Work Discipline as Intervening Variable (Case Study at Industrial Research and Development Agency)

Kharis Mugiono¹, Parwoto²
Magister of Management¹, Postgraduate Lecturer²
Mercu Buana University, Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:-The era of globalization provides major challenges that must be faced by organizations, where organizations are required to be able to adapt and move towards the dynamics of change. The role of leadership is very important in making changes through policies and increasing employee competence so that they are able to work more optimally so as to be able to encourage the creation of good work discipline and have an impact on improving employee and organizational performance. The purpose of this study was to analyze the influence of Leadership and Competence on Employee Performance mediated by Work Discipline (Case Study at Industrial Research and Development Agency). The number of samples used in this study were 104 respondents. The data analysis method in this study uses Structural Equation Modeling – Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) with the Smart PLS application (V.3.2.9). Based on the results of this study indicate that Work Discipline is able to mediate partially (partial mediation) the indirect effect of Leadership and Competence on Employee Performance. Leadership, Competence and Work Discipline have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance. Leadership and Competence have a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline.

Keywords:-Leadership, Competence, Work Discipline, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Massive technological developments have entered the industrial revolution 4.0 which has greatly assisted humans in their daily activities. With a dynamic digital transformation, it is believed that it can improve quality and is predicted to be able to make social changes in various aspects of life. Therefore, every organization, both government and private, is required to be able to adapt to technological advances in order to achieve organizational goals.

The quality of the human resources employed to plan, carry out, and control the organization in question also has a significant part in determining how successful a given organization will be (Manullang, 2015). Human resources (HR) is an important factor in moving and controlling other management elements such as Money, Materials, Machines, Methods and Markets because their roles and functions cannot be replaced by other resources.

To ensure that all employee performance contributes to meeting organizational performance goals, the government, through the Ministry of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform, has issued Minister Regulation of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform with Number 8 of 2021 regarding the Civil Servant Performance Management System. Every government agency must implement a civil servant performance management system. The Industrial Research and Development Agency (called as BPPI), one of the echelon I work units at the Ministry of Industry, which has the task of conducting research and development in the industrial sector, is also required to be professional in dealing with various problems that hinder current and future industrial development. BPPI seeks to improve unit performance to provide optimal service to stakeholders. The following is the data from BPPI's performance assessment results for the 2016-2019 period:

No	WORK UNIT	2016	2017	2018	2019
1	Secretariat General	87.75	81.91	81.99	73.31
2	Directorate General of Agro Industry	85.93	85.57	80.59	69.19
3	Directorate General of Chemical, Textile and Multifarious Industries	85.96	82.19	80.48	72.26
4	Directorate General of Metal, Machinery, Transportation Equipment, and Electronics Industry	80.43	81.09	76.14	66.81
5	Directorate General of Small and Medium Industries	83.96	78.65	81.04	75.1
6	Directorate General of Resilience and Development of International Industrial Access	78.76	85.83	80.78	61.67
7	Inspectorate General	85.73	87.08	84.33	78.76
8	Industrial Research and Development Agency (BPPI)	89	83.56	85.94	80.38
9	Directorate General of Industrial Regional Development (Since 2019 Merged with Another Director General)	76.25	73.32	67.61	
	Industrial Human Resource Development Agency (Born Since 2019)				66.19
	Total	753.78	739.2	718.9	643.68
	Average value	83.75	82.13	79.88	71.52

Table 1: Performance Assessment Results in Echelon I Work Units at the Ministry of Industry for 2016-2019 Period

Source : Internal Data (2021)

Based on the results of the 2016-2019 Echelon I Unit Performance Assessment at the Ministry of Industry, the 2016-2019 BPPI performance evaluation results were 89.00, 83.56, 85.94 and 80.38 respectively, meaning that over four years it had decreased by 8.62 points.

Individual performance and organizational performance, or firm performance, are closely related in this situation. In other words, it is likely that the company will perform well if the person performs well. If an employee has high knowledge (competence), is motivated to work because he is paid in accordance with the contract, and has improved future prospects, his performance is good (career). Employees are motivated to carry out work tasks with high performance when they are concerned about their salaries and expectations. Good organizational performance will be influenced by the performance of a group of employees and their superiors (Sedarmayanti, 2017).

The researchers searched for literature references and conducted a study survey to learn about and examine the elements that affect performance. Employee performance is influenced by a number of variables, including their knowledge, motivation at work, leadership style, organizational culture, work ethic, work environment, personality, loyalty, and dedication, according to Kasmir (2016). Competence is also required, in addition to the aforementioned elements, to assist the business in fostering a culture of high performance. Performance will improve when human resources apply more competencies (Wibowo, 2017).

Based on the findings of a study survey conducted with 30 employees of the Industrial Research and Development Agency (BPPI), who were asked for their opinions on 3 (three) variables that were strongly suspected of influencing performance at BPPI. BPPI staff performance is influenced by 10 (ten) different elements, according to the pre-survey data.

No.	Factors Effecting Performance	Amount	Percentage (%)
1	Organizational change	7	7.78%
2	Leadership	12	13.33%
3	Organizational Commitment	9	10.00%
4	Work Discipline	11	12.22%
5	Competence	15	16.67%
6	Organizational culture	8	8.89%
7	Work environment	5	5.56%
8	Job satisfaction	10	11.11%
9	Work motivation	6	6.67%
10	Workload	7	7.78%
	TOTAL		100.00%

Table 2: Factors Effecting Employee Performance at BPPI

Source: Pre-survey date (2021)

The 3 variables that are thought to have the strongest influence based on the pre-survey are Leadership (13.33%), Competence (16.67%), and Work Discipline (12.22%).

No.	Variable	Statement	Yes (%)	No (%)
1	Leadership	Leaders always provide clear directions to employees	14 46.67	16 53.33
		Leaders always motivate employees	13 43.33	17 56.67
2	Competence	Training helps work better	15 50.00	15 50.00
		Education influences career development	12 40.00	18 60.00
3	Work Discipline	Employees always come on time	13 43.33	17 56.67
		Employees always work to meet targets	16 53.33	14 46.67

Table 3: Variables that Effect employee performance at BPPI

Source: Pre-survey date (2021)

Based on table 3 above, leadership elasticity is not maximized because 53.33% of respondents think that superiors do not always provide real guidance to employees and superiors do not always provide encouragement to employees of 56.67% of respondents; elastic competence proves that it is not optimal yet visible from some respondents who feel nursery training helps to do better work, only 50% of respondents and 60% of respondents feel learning does not affect job development; and elastic adherence to activities which proves that 56.67% of respondents think employees do not always arrive on time and 53.33% of respondents think that there are still many employees who are always on duty to meet targets.

There are still variances or results from before research, as evidenced by a number of earlier studies on leadership, competence, work discipline, and employee performance. Research on leadership variables, Indraningsih, et al. (2020) found that leadership has a positive and significant relationship to employee performance, however Sukmawati and Alam (2019) found a negative and not significant relationship between leadership and performance employee. According to Widodo, et al. (2021), research on competency variables shows that competency effects employee performance, but according to Rostina, et al. (2020), claim that competency to performance employee has a negative and not significant relations. Research related to work discipline variable, Fachrudi, et al (2021) claims that work discipline has a positive effect on employee performance, whereas according to Kelimeda, et al (2018) states that work discipline has no significant effect on employee performance.

The authors suggest a study titled "The Effect of Leadership and Competence on Employee Performance with Work Discipline as Intervening Variable (Case Study at Industrial Research and Development Agency)" based on the phenomena, pre-surveys, and research gaps in this study.

II. LITERATURE REVIEWS

A. Employee Performance

Mangkunegara (2012) claims that an employee's performance is the end result of the quality and quantity of work completed while carrying out the obligations assigned to employees. Sutrisno (2016) asserts that performance is the outcome of employee work evaluated in terms of quality, quantity, working hours, and cooperation to meet organizational objectives. Fahmi (2017) explains that based on established conditions or agreements, the performance is a process's results refers to and is measured over a specific amount of time.

Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara (2012) states that dimensions and indicators play a crucial role in research. The dimensions of the factors that go into determining how well employees perform are as follows: 1) work quality is how well an employee does what he is supposed to do; 2) work quantity is how long a person is on duty in one day. The number of quantity can be observed from the dexterity of each employee's activities; 3) Job responsibility is an understanding of the employee's role in carrying out the work provided by the company; 4) Cooperation is the desire of employees to participate with other employees or employees in a straight and horizontal manner both inside and outside the profession so that the results of the activity continue to be good; 5) Initiatives from within employees themselves to carry out work and resolve problems at the job site without waiting for orders from the leadership or demonstrating responsibility in the job which has become its responsibility.

B. Work Discipline

According to Siswanto (2013), work discipline is an attitude of respect, appreciate, adherence and obedience to applicable rules, both written and unwritten, and the ability to carry them out in order to avoid sanctions if he violates the tasks and authority delegated. According to Rivai (2011), work discipline is a method managers use to communicate with staff in an effort to change a behavior and to raise awareness and commitment to abide by all company rules. Work discipline, according to Malayu SP Hasibuan (2019), is the awareness of and willingness to follow all corporate policies and existing social norms.

Siswanto (2013) asserts that an organization's discipline has the following dimensions: 1) The Frequency of Attendance: one of the benchmarks to determine the level of employee attendance. the higher the level of employee presence, the higher the employee's discipline; 2) The level of alertness of employees: Employees who in carrying out their profession are always full of calculation and accuracy have a high level of understanding of themselves and their profession; 3) Adherence to work standards: In carrying out their profession, employees must comply with all activity standards that have been formalized in accordance with the provisions and principles of activity so that activity accidents are not exist or can be avoided; 4) Obedience to work regulations: intended for comfort and smooth running of work; 5) Work ethic: needed by every employee in carrying out their profession so that a harmonious atmosphere is created, mutual respect for each employee.

C. Leadership

Leadership, according to Schermerhorn (2011), is the process of inspiring others to put in a lot of effort to complete eventful duties. Leadership, according to Yukl (2015), is the process of encouraging people to comprehend and concur on what is necessary to carry out duties and how to carry them out, as well as the process of synergizing both individual and group hard work to reach shared goals.

In order to accomplish goals, leadership involves using communication to influence a large number of individuals. This is accomplished through influencing others through commands, directions, and acts that prompt others to behave or react favorably, produce significant dynamic forces that can inspire and organize groups in order to accomplish goals. (Dubrin in Busro, 2020).

According to Schermerhorn (in Edison, et al., 2018), leadership has the following dimensions: 1) Having a clear strategy: the leader carries out and/or has a major and directed change plan against the vision, mission and strategy of the organization and communicates it well to its members; 2) Concern: the leader has concern for every problem faced by members and motivates them, as well as

concern for the environment and work comfort; 3) Stimulating members: the leader stimulates and helps members for positive goals and invites them to avoid unproductive things with a fun approach, and members accept and realize the benefits for personal and organizational; 4) Maintain team cohesiveness: the leader always maintains team cohesiveness and does not want to be trapped in the thoughts of members who want to seek personal sympathy by cornering others. Opportunity for it is not tolerated. He unites and synergizes the potential of the team's rifts to become an extraordinary and harmonious force; 5) Respect for differences and beliefs: the leader respects every difference of opinion for a better direction, and invites to respect differences and beliefs to all members.

D. Competence

According to Spencer and Spencer (1993), competence is the fundamental building block of a person's qualities and denotes behaviors or methods of thinking, comparing circumstances, and supporting for a long time. While Competence is the primary quality possessed by the most successful people in every field of profession, according to Kessler in his book (2011), is what has enabled him to achieve. The capacity based on skills and knowledge and backed by the work attitude required by the job to carry out or complete a job or task is defined as competence by Wibowo (2017).

Spencer and Spencer (in Wibowo, 2017) states that there are five (five) different types of competence characteristics, which will also be employed as research dimensions in this study. These characteristics are as follows: 1) A motive is something that is invariably thought or desired by someone who causes an action; 2) Traits are physical characters and assumptions that don't change to circumstances or data; 3) Self-concept is a person's feelings, views, attitude, and judgments about himself; 4) Knowledge is data about a specific aspect that people have; 5) Skills is the ability to carry out certain physical or psychological obligations.

E. Framework

Based on all the explanations regarding the relationship between the variables above, the framework of this research is as follows:

Fig. 1: Thinking Framework

F. Hypothesis

- H1: Leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BPPI
- H2: Competence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BPPI
- H3: Leadership has a positive and significant effect on work discipline at BPPI
- H4: Competence has a positive and significant effect on work discipline at BPPI
- H5: Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BPPI
- H6: Leadership has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Work Discipline at BPPI
- H7: Competence has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Work Discipline at BPPI

III. RESEARCH AND METHOD

A descriptive method with a quantitative approach and a causal research design was employed in this study. Descriptive studies, as defined by Sekaran and Bougie (2016), are studies that are frequently created to gather information that describes the features of objects like people, organizations, products or brands, events, or circumstances. Sugiyono (2016) describes quantitative research as a type of research that uses quantitative or statistical analysis to assess pre-existing hypotheses. It is founded on the positivist ideology and is used to study certain populations or samples. According to Zikmund, et al.(2013), a tool for identifying causal relationships is referred to as causal research.

A. Population and Sample

Sugiyono (2016) claims that the population is a generalization area made up of things or individuals that fit certain criteria that were established by researchers in order to be studied and then used to derive conclusions. All 140 personnel of the Industrial Research and Development Agency (called as BPPI), located at the Ministry of Industry's headquarters, comprised this study's population.

Probability sampling is the method of choice because it gives every component or person in the population an equal chance of being chosen as a sample (Sugiyono, 2016). Proportionate stratified random sampling is the kind of probability approach utilized. This sample method is utilized for populations that contain individuals or elements that are not homogeneous and are proportionally stratified, according to Sugiyono (2016). The researcher calculated the sample size using the Slovin formula with a 5% error tolerance level, yielding a total of 104 respondents for the study.

B. Method of Data Collection

In this study, the source of data in this study was primary data and secondary data (Sugiarto, 2017). Primary data is a source of research data obtained directly from interviews with informants and respondents' statements that were extracted using a questionnaire according to the variables studied at the research location. Meanwhile, secondary data is obtained indirectly from sources such as books, literature, documentation or written records belonging to agencies.

C. Method of Data Analysis

This study uses the method of analysis with Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) and instrument testing using the method Partial Least Square (PLS) with help SmartPLS software version 3.2.9. PLS is used to explain whether there is a relationship between latent variables (predictions) (Ghozali, 2011). In this study to test the indicators using the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) technique.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Characteristics of Respondents

This section will explain the grouping of respondents based on certain characteristics. The characteristics of the respondents are used to see and know the descriptions of the various respondents based on gender, age range, level of education, and years of service.

Categories	Options	Number of Respondents	Percentages	Total Percentages
Gender	Male	68	65.38%	100%
	Female	36	34.62%	
age	< 21 years old	0	0.00%	100%
	21 – 35 years old	40	38.46%	
	36 – 45 years old	45	43.27%	
	> 45 years old	19	18.27%	
Education Level	Senior High School/D1	13	12.50%	100%
	D3/S1	59	56.73%	
	S2	32	30.77%	
Long Period	≤ 2 years	2	1.92%	100%
	2 – 5 years	26	25.00%	
	5 – 10 years	14	13.46%	
	≥ 10 years	62	59.62%	

Table 4: Characteristics of Respondents

Source: Data Calculation

Based on table 4, it indicates that 65.38% or as many as 68 male employees dominate more than female employees at 34.62% or as many as 36 employees. Based on level education is seen 43.27% or as many as 45 employees with an age group between 36-45 years dominate more than employees with other age groups, while there is no age group under 21 years. That D3 and or S1 employees make up 56.73%, or up to 59 employees, more than employees with other educational levels, whereas senior high school and or D1 employees are only 12.50%, or up to 13 employees, of the workforce. The last, 62 people, or 59.62% of all employees, have tenures of 10 years or more, compared to just 2 employee for having 2 years of tenure or less.

B. The Measurement Model Evaluation (Outer Model)

Based on the loading factor value for each construct, the study data must adhere to the standards of validity and reliability in order to pass evaluation of the measurement model stage (Outer Model). If the outer model can describe the link between latent variables and their indicators, it is said to be successful. Utilizing the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) technique, the indicators in this study were tested.

In this study, a Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was conducted on the latent construct and the outer model by examining the size or value of validity and reliability. Measures of discriminant and convergent validity were used to assess the validity of the data, while Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability were used to assess the reliability.

Following reduction, the PLS algorithm's calculations are completed, and the following path model is generated:

Fig. 2: Path Model with Loading Factor after Reduction

Source: Output of SmartPLS 3

C. Convergent Validity

By evaluating the AVE value and the loading factor value of each construct, convergent validity testing is performed. A loading factor greater than 0.70 indicates that an indicator has a high level of validity, according to Ghozali & Latan (2015: 76).

	Leadership	Competence	Work Discipline	Performance	Description
KEP.08	0.804				Valid
KEP.09	0.756				Valid
KEP. 11	0.827				Valid
KEP.12	0.790				Valid
KOM. 01		0.814			Valid
KOM. 08		0.755			Valid
KOM. 09		0.803			Valid
KOM. 11		0.763			Valid
DK. 01			0.728		Valid
DK. 02			0.798		Valid
DK. 06			0.794		Valid
DK. 07			0.813		Valid
KIN. 02				0.733	Valid
KIN. 03				0.725	Valid
KIN. 05				0.752	Valid
KIN. 06				0.757	Valid
KIN. 08				0.738	Valid
KIN. 10				0.770	Valid
KIN. 12				0.730	Valid

Table 5: Outer Loadings

Source: Output of SmartPLS 3

Based on the findings of the convergence validity experiment, Table 5 proves that the markers on the Loading Factors (Outer Loadings) benchmark have met the trial

validity threshold of more than 0.7. This shows that the symptoms are still relevant and used in a form.

Variables	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Leadership	0.631
Competence	0.615
Work Discipline	0.615
Performance	0.553

Table 6. AVE (Average Variance Extracted)

Source : Output of SmartPLS 3

Table 6 of the results of the convergent validity experiment above using the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) benchmark shows that all constructs pass the validity test with an AVE number of more than 0.5.

D. Discriminant Validity

When determining whether a marker will have a higher number in the construct it produces than the other constructs, the validity of the discriminant is used. Through the use of the Cross Loading benchmark and the Fornell-Larcker Criterion, discriminant validity testing is made possible.

	Leadership	Competence	Work Discipline	Performance
KEP.08	0.804	0.585	0.570	0.576
KEP.09	0.756	0.531	0.518	0.388
KEP. 11	0.827	0.553	0.572	0.562
KEP.12	0.790	0.526	0.520	0.543
KOM. 01	0.498	0.814	0.525	0.490
KOM. 08	0.619	0.755	0.622	0.551
KOM. 09	0.530	0.803	0.517	0.563
KOM. 11	0.508	0.763	0.558	0.602
DK. 01	0.475	0.551	0.728	0.484
DK. 02	0.496	0.490	0.798	0.596
DK. 06	0.599	0.540	0.794	0.503
DK. 07	0.577	0.642	0.813	0.661
KIN. 02	0.456	0.478	0.516	0.733
KIN. 03	0.513	0.548	0.543	0.725
KIN. 05	0.488	0.541	0.502	0.752
KIN. 06	0.441	0.439	0.494	0.757
KIN. 08	0.499	0.569	0.539	0.738
KIN. 10	0.457	0.527	0.516	0.770
KIN. 12	0.551	0.559	0.624	0.730

Table 7: Cross Loadings

Source: Output of SmartPLS 3

Based on table 7 above, all loading markers that pass the discriminant validity test using the cross-loading benchmark have fulfilled the cross-loading benchmark

validity requirements. This proves that each construct marker has a greater relationship value than the contents of the other constructs.

	leadership	Competence	Work Discipline	performance
Leadership	0.795			
Competence	0.691	0.784		
Work Discipline	0.687	0.712	0.784	
performance	0.658	0.707	0.721	0.744

Table 8: Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Source: Output of SmartPLS 3

According to table 8 above, all of the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) root values for the construct that satisfy the validity requirements are the results of discriminant validity testing with the Fornell-Larcker Criterion parameter. This demonstrates that each construct's AVE root

already has a higher correlation value than the other constructions' AVE roots do.

E. Internal Consistency Reliability

Another test to evaluate the measurement model is to look at the reliability of the construct. According to Ghozali & Latan (2015), in PLS-SEM to measure the reliability of a

construct with reflexive indicators can be done in 2 ways, namely *Composite Reliability* and *Cronbach's Alpha*. Constructs are declared reliable if they have *Composite Reliability value and Cronbach's Alpha value* above 0.70.

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Leadership	0.808	0.873
Competence	0.791	0.864
Work Discipline	0.791	0.864
Performance	0.865	0.897

Table 9: Internal Consistency Reliability

Source : Output of SmartPLS 3

Testing the Internal Consistency Reliability with the Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha parameters in table 9 shows that all constructs have fulfilled the reliability criteria in the Composite Reliability parameter and Cronbach's Alpha parameters by showing a value above 0.7.

F. Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

According to Ghozali (2014) Structural models show the strength of estimates between latent or construct variables. The structural model evaluation stage is carried out to determine the model hypothesis on the research data. After calculating the reduced PLS Algorithm, the path coefficient value is obtained which describes the strength of the relationship between constructs/variables as shown in the following figure.

Fig. 2: Bootstrapping Path Model

Source: Output of SmartPLS 3

G. R-Square

To gauge how well the model can account for the fluctuation in the dependent variable, the coefficient of determination (R²) is used (Ghozali, 2014). The shortcoming of R-squared itself is its nature, which is improved by the addition of variables. When evaluating an

exogenous construct's capacity to explain endogenous constructs, adjusted R Square value paints a clearer picture than R Square. Because of the adjusted R square's consideration of the quantity of variables and data samples, this study uses the adjusted R square value.

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Work Discipline	0.580	0.571
Performance	0.612	0.600

Table 10: R-Square and R-Square Adjusted

Source: Output of SmartPLS 3

According to table 10 above, the corrected R-square value for the work discipline variable is 0.571, which means that leadership and competence affect 57.1% of employee work discipline while other factors influence 42.9% of employee performance. The performance variable's modified R-square value is 0.600, which means that leadership, competency, and work ethic together account for 60.0% of employee performance, with other factors

accounting for the remaining 40.0% of employee performance.

H. f-Square (f²)

According to Cohen (1988), exogenous latent variables have a minor, moderate, and substantial effect on the structural level, with recommended Effect Sizes (f²) of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35. The following table illustrates how external latent factors affect endogenous latent variables:

	Effect Size (f²)	Description
Leadership (X1)→Performance (Y2)	0.040	weak
Competence (X2)→Performance (Y2)	0.107	weak
Leadership (X1)→Work Discipline (Y1)	0.172	Medium
Competence (X2)→Work Discipline (Y1)	0.258	Medium
Work Discipline (Y1)→Performance (Y2)	0.146	weak

Table 11: f-Square

Source: Output of SmartPLS 3

I. Goodness of Fit Index (GoF)

The SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual) criterion, a measurement of the absolute value of the mean residual covariance, was employed in this investigation.

This metric evaluates the size of the discrepancy between the studied correlations and the absolute measurements predicted by the relevant model. The GoF test results, which are 0.10, seem good enough.

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model	Cut Off	Results
SRMR	0.08	0.08	<0.10	Good Enough

Table 12: GoF Models

Source : Output of SmartPLS 3

J. Predictive Relevance (Q²)

According to Ghazali (2014) Predictive relevance used to test the model how good the resulting observation value. If

the Q square value > 0, it can be said to have a good observation value, whereas if the Q square value < 0, it can be said that the observation value is not good.

Endogenous Variables	SSO	SSE	Q² (=1-SSE/SSO)	Fit Models
Work Discipline	416	272,723	0.344	Moderate
Performance	728	492,238	0.324	Moderate

Table 13: Construct Cross validated Redundancy

Source: Output of SmartPLS 3

According to table 13 above, that the endogenous variable of Work Discipline (Y1) and the endogenous variable of Performance (Y2) have a predictive relevance value (Q²) > 0, namely 0.344 and 0.324 so that it can be concluded that this study has an observational value (Chin, 1998).

K. Hypothesis Test

According to the criteria for testing the hypothesis, there is a significant effect of exogenous factors on endogenous variables if the value of t-statistics is greater than the value of t-table (1.96), or if the p-value is greater than the value of significant alpha 5% or 0.05. The description that follows will help you understand the outcomes of the significance and model testing.

	Coefficient	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P-Values
KEP(X1)→KIN(Y2)	0.187	2.126	0.034
COM(X2)→KIN(Y2)	0.316	3,738	0.000
KEP(X1)→DK(Y1)	0.372	3,149	0.002
COM(X2)→DK(Y1)	0.455	3,889	0.000
DK(Y1)→KIN(Y2)	0.368	3,518	0.000
KEP(X1)→DK(Y1)→KIN(Y2)	0.137	2,666	0.008
COM(X2)→DK(Y1)→KIN(Y2)	0.167	2,385	0.017

Table 14: Hypothesis Test

Source: Output of SmartPLS 3

- the results of the H1 testing produce output with a value of path coefficient of 0.187, a value t-statistic of 2.126 > t-table 1.96, and a p-value = 0.034 <0.05, so it can be interpreted that there is a significant and positive effect of the leadership variable on employee performance.
- the results of the H2 testing produce output with a value of path coefficient of 0.316, a value t-statistic of 3.738 > t-table 1.96, and a p-value = 0.000 <0.05, so it can be interpreted that there is a significant and positive effect of the competence variable on employee performance.
- the results of the H3 testing produce output with a value of path coefficient of 0.372, a value t-statistic of 3.149 > t-table 1.96, and a p-value = 0.002 <0.05, so it can be interpreted that there is a significant and positive effect of the leadership variable on work discipline.
- the results of the H4 testing produce output with a value of path coefficient of 0.455, a value t-statistic of 3.889 > t-table 1.96, and a p-value = 0.000 <0.05, so it can be interpreted that there is a significant and positive effect of the leadership variable on work discipline.
- the results of the H5 testing produce output with a value of path coefficient of 0.368, a value t-statistic of 3.518 > t-table 1.96, and a p-value = 0.000 <0.05, so it can be interpreted that there is a significant and positive effect of the work discipline variable on employee performance.
- the results of the H6 testing produce output with a value of path coefficient of 0.137, a value t-statistic of 2.666 > t-table 1.96, and a p-value = 0.008 <0.05, so it can be interpreted that there is a significant and positive effect of the leadership variable on employee performance through work discipline.
- the results of the H7 testing produce output with a value of path coefficient of 0.167, a value t-statistic of 2.385 > t-table 1.96, and a p-value = 0.017 <0.05, so it can be interpreted that there is a significant and positive effect of the competence variable on employee performance through work discipline.

L. Discussion

According to testing first hypothesis, leadership positively effects BPPI employees' performance, with the indicator that has the biggest impact being the leader's ability to handle member issues amicably. This demonstrates that there is a healthy working relationship between employees with the leadership's engagement in fostering peaceful and stable working circumstances among employees so that workers can effectively collaborate and coordinate in an effort to increase employee performance at BPPI. According to research by Turay, et al. (2019), there is

a significant relationship between leadership and employee performance that is partially and simultaneously influenced, if leadership is improving, employee performance will improve as well. The same conclusion was reached in a different study by Pawirosumarto, et al. (2017), Irdaningsih, et al. (2020), and Paais & Patiruhu (2020). Leadership has a favorable and significant impact on employee performance. This supports the study's first hypothesis, which argues that "leadership has a positive and significant effect on performance".

Competence has a positive effect on improving the performance of BPPI employees with the indicator that has the strongest influence being the readiness of employees to carry out the tasks given by the leadership. This indicates that employees will always be ready to accept and carry out tasks from the leadership properly according to their abilities so that employee performance will also increase. According to the findings of earlier research by Parashakti, et al. (2019), there is a significant correlation between competence and performance, with the better an employee's competence, the better the employee's performance. According to this research, employee performance is positively and significantly influenced by competence, with higher competence levels translating into higher performance (Kartika and Sugiarto, 2014; Ahmad, 2016; Nguyen, et al., 2020). This supports the study's second hypothesis, which claims that "competence has a positive and significant effect on performance."

Leadership has a positive influence in improving the Work Discipline of BPPI employees with the strongest indicator being that leaders can resolve internal conflicts well. With the authority they have, the leadership can exert influence to increase employee awareness and willingness in the Work Discipline of BPPI employees. The role of leadership through policies such as reward and punishment will encourage employees to be more obedient to work regulations. Therefore, the increasing influence of Leadership will further increase Work Discipline simultaneously. In line with previous research conducted by Timtami, et al. (2012), Jaya and Adnyani (2015), and Calista and Maimunah (2020) show that transformational leadership partially has a positive and significant effect on employee work discipline. Like the research conducted by Affini (2021) shows that the results of the study show that there is a positive and significant direct effect between leadership on work discipline. Thus, third hypothesis in this study which states that "leadership on work discipline has a positive and significant effect" is accepted.

Competence has a positive effect in increasing the Work Discipline of BPPI employees with the indicator that has the strongest effect being the readiness of employees to carry out the tasks given by the leadership. With the competence they have, employees will consider the consequences that will occur if they violate discipline and they tend to be ashamed if they commit a violation. Therefore, the increasing influence of Competence will simultaneously increase Work Discipline. The research results of Arif Firdaus, et al. (2017) claims that there is a positive and significant effect of the competence variable on work discipline, meaning that if employee competency is increased, the work it will be easy and achievable to work effectively and efficiently, so that the employee's work discipline will also increase. The results of the same research were also carried out by Achmad, et al. (2016) and Arif Bagus Widodo, et al. (2021) which showed that competence affects employee work discipline, where increasing employee competence can encourage employee work discipline. Thus, fourth hypothesis in this study which claims that "competence on work discipline has a positive and significant effect" is accepted.

Work Discipline has a beneficial effect on enhancing BPPI employee performance, with compliance with work regulations having the biggest impact. Since of the high levels of incentive from the leadership, the degree of education, and the money earned, work discipline is crucial to enhancing employee performance because without it, performance will be subpar. Workplace regulations and procedures will always be followed by employees who have a work-discipline attitude. These employees will also make an effort to reach their performance goals, never arrive late for work, and complete their tasks on schedule. As a result, Work Discipline's growing effect will simultaneously boost Performance. According to the test results from this study, work discipline has a favorable, statistically significant impact on employee performance. This is consistent with earlier research by Aprizal, et al. (2018) came to the conclusion that discipline had a positive and significant impact on employee performance based on the data processing results. According to Meilany and Ibrahim (2015), Hanafi Suyukoh et al. (2021), and Agustriani et al. (2022) reveal that work discipline has a favorable and significant impact on employee performance. As a result, the study's hypothesis number five—that "work discipline has a positive and significant effect on performance"—is accepted.

Leadership has effect indirectly on performance through the mediation of Work Discipline of BPPI employees, where Work Discipline is able to mediate the influence of Leadership in a positive direction and is able to explain its significant effect on Performance. Good leadership is able to direct, control, and encourage employees to maintain solid internal relationships and maintain togetherness within the team, thereby reducing internal conflicts. Through the Work Discipline enforcement policy, employees will comply with work regulations such as attendance levels, achievement of employee work goals, and accuracy in completing tasks. It can be interpreted that, the increasing influence of leadership mediated by work

discipline will further improve employee performance. According to earlier research from Sobariah, et al. (2018), the findings of his study demonstrate that transformational leadership has a favorable and significant impact on employee performance through work discipline and is categorized as full mediation (VAF results 0.5485). Better leadership has a higher impact on work discipline, which influences employee performance (Ndolu, et al., 2022; Setiadi and Lutfi, 2021; Barkhowa, et al., 2017). Because of this, sixth hypothesis which reads, "performance is significantly and positively effected by leadership through work discipline", is accepted in this study.

Competence has an indirect effect on performance through the mediation of employee work discipline at BPPI, where work discipline is able to mediate the effect of competence in a positive direction and is able to explain its significant effect on performance. Competence can align work and organizational behavior, where competence can assist employees in carrying out the tasks given by the leadership and provide more optimal work results. Leadership policies in making work regulations will be able to improve employee work discipline. If employee competence is supported by an attitude of work discipline, it will have an even greater impact on improving the performance of BPPI employees. It can be interpreted that, the increasing effect of Competence mediated by Work Discipline will further increase Performance simultaneously. The findings of this study are consistent with Sujana's (2020) research, The Effect of Compensation and Competence on Employee Performance with Work Discipline as an Intervening Variable at the Palembang City Industrial Service, which demonstrates that Competence on Employee Performance at the Palembang City Industrial Service has an indirect effect on Work Discipline as a mediating variable or intermediary variable as evidenced by a P-Value of 0.001 0. The findings of the same study conducted by Rapika and Sulaiman (2020) and Eliza et al. (2022) demonstrate that work discipline can moderate the impact of competency on employee performance. Thus, the seventh hypothesis which reads, "performance is significantly and positively effected by competence through work discipline", is accepted in this study.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

A. Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and discussion in the previous chapters, several conclusions can be put forward as follows:

- Leadership has directly a positive and significant effect on the performance of employee at BPPI. This means that the greater the role of the leadership can contribute to improving the performance of BPPI employees.
- Competence has directly a positive and significant effect on the performance of employee at BPPI. This means that due to the increase in competence, it can increase the performance of BPPI employees.
- Leadership directly effects positively and significantly on the work discipline of BPPI employees. Thus, by increasing the effect of leadership, it can make a better contribution to the work discipline of BPPI employees.

- Competence directly effects positively and significantly on the work discipline of BPPI employees. Thus, by increasing the effect of competence, this can have an impact on increasing the discipline of BPPI employees at work.
- Work discipline directly has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BPPI. That means that the greater the influence of work discipline, the higher the increase of employee performance at BPPI.
- Work discipline is able to mediate leadership effect on employee performance at BPPI partially (partial mediation). Therefore, the increase of leadership effect through work discipline is able to improve the performance of BPPI employees simultaneously.
- Work discipline is able to mediate competence effect on employee performance at BPPI partially (partial mediation). Therefore, the increase of competence effect through work discipline is able to improve the performance of BPPI employees simultaneously.

B. Recommendations

Based on the discussion and conclusions above, the variables of leadership, competence, and work discipline are able to provide a good role and contribution in efforts to improve employee performance at BPPI, where BPPI as an organization seeks to evaluate and improve employee performance improvement. Therefore, the author conveys several suggestions, including the following:

- Leadership is the core of a management because leaders have a big role in influencing the BPPI organization. Things that need to be done by management/leaders to improve their leadership role include: a) optimizing the involvement of all employees to participate and be active in the activities carried out by their work units; b) conduct counseling to understand any difficulties experienced by employees at work.
- *The importance of employee competence in an organization can contribute to and improve the performance of BPPI employees. Things that can be done by management/leaders in improving the competence of BPPI employees include: a) providing opportunities and/or facilitating them to attend education and training as needed to support their job duties; b) provide opportunities and/or facilitate continuing education to a higher level; c) holding knowledge sharing by presenting competent sources from internal and external.*
- Based on the results of this study, it shows that work discipline can directly influence performance and is able to mediate the influence of leadership and competence in improving employee performance at BPPI. Things that can be done by management/leaders in improving the work discipline of BPPI employees include: a) implementing balanced rewards and punishments for all BPPI employees; b) monitor and evaluate employee discipline periodically to determine the level of employee discipline.
- For further research, there are several suggestions that can be submitted as follows: a) expand research on central and regional government agencies with a larger scope such as in one ministry / institution; b) developing research with a larger sample size on the effect of the same

variable on employee performance; c) develop a causality relationship model with the influence of different variables outside the variables in this study.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Achmad, A., Umar, A., & Budiman, B. (2018). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja dan Kompetensi terhadap Kinerja Pegawai melalui Disiplin Kerja. *Jurnal Mirai Management*, 3(2), 92-119.
- [2.] Achmad, S. H. (2017). The Effect of Competency, Motivation, and Organizational Culture on The Employee Performance at The Jayakarta Hotel Bandung, Indonesia. *Journal of Business on Hospitality and Tourism*, 2(1), 120-130.
- [3.] Affini, D. N. (2021). Analysis of Employee's Work Discipline in PT Cipta Pedagang Unggul from Motivation and Leadership Style. *Dinasti International Journal of Economics, Finance & Accounting*, 1(6), 1112-1123.
- [4.] Agustriani, R., Ratnasari, S. L., & Zamora, R. (2022). Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja, Komunikasi, Motivasi Kerja, dan Lingkungan Kerja terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *Jurnal Trias Politika*, 6(1), 104-122.
- [5.] Aprizal, A., Kurniaty, K., & Hasriani, H. (2020). Pengaruh Kedisiplinan terhadap Kinerja Karyawan pada PT Telkomsel Area IV Pamasuka Kota Makassar. *e-Journal Ekonomi Bisnis dan Akuntansi*, 7(2), 131-135.
- [6.] Barkhowa, M. K., Lukiastuti, F., & Sutanto, H. A. (2017). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan terhadap Kinerja Karyawan dengan Kedisiplinan Karyawan sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi pada Karyawan Bagian Produksi dan Galvanis di PT. Kurnia Adijaya Mandiri). *Jurnal Magisma*, 5(1), 24-37.
- [7.] Busro, Muhammad. (2018). *Teori-Teori Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: Prenadamedia Group.
- [8.] Calista, A., & Maimunah, S. (2020). Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan terhadap Disiplin Kerja Karyawan pada Kantor Pengelolaan Hutan Produksi Unit IV Meranti, Kecamatan Tungkal Jaya. *Jurnal Manajemen Kompeten*, 3(1), 1-11.
- [9.] Chin, W. W. (1998). The Partial Least Squares Approach to Structural Equation. *Modeling. Modern Methods for Business Research*, 295-336. London: : Lawrence Earlbaum Associates.
- [10.] Cohen, Jacob. (1988). *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences* (2nd. Edition). Hillsdale, New Jersey: Lawrence Earlbaum Associates.
- [11.] Edison, Emron., Komariyah, Imas., dan Anwar, Yohny. (2018). *Manajemen Sumber. Daya Manusia*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- [12.] Eliza, Y., Andria, Y., & Adriani, E. (2022). Model Peningkatan Kinerja melalui Disiplin Kerja sebagai Intervening pada Pegawai Dinas Pendidikan Kota Padang. *J-MAS (Jurnal Manajemen dan Sains)*, 7(1), 333-339.
- [13.] Fachrudi, F., Parwoto, P., & Saluy, Ahmad Badawi. (2021). The Influence of Leadership and Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance Through Working Disciplines as

- Intervening Variables. *Dinasti International Journal of Management Science*, 3(1), 1-22.
- [14.] Fahmi, Irham. (2017). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Bandung : Alfabeta.
- [15.] Firdaus, A., Nuryanti, N., & Rama, R. (2017). Pengaruh Pemberian Insentif, Kompetensi, dan Beban Kerja terhadap Disiplin Kerja Karyawan pada PT Bank Tabungan Pensiun Negara Cabang Pekanbaru (Doctoral dissertation, Riau University). *Jurnal Online Mahasiswa Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Riau*, 4(1), 311-322.
- [16.] Ghozali, Imam dan Latan, Hengky. (2015). *Partial Least Squares: Konsep, Teknik, dan Aplikasi Menggunakan Program SmartPLS 3.0*. Semarang: BP UNDIP.
- [17.] Ghozali, Imam. (2014). *Structural Equation Modeling Metode Alternatif dengan Partial Least Square (PLS)*. Semarang: BP UNDIP.
- [18.] Hasibuan, Malayu S.P. (2019). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, Edisi Revisi*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- [19.] Irdaningsih, H., Parwoto, P., & Saluy, Ahmad Badawi. (2020). Influence of Leadership, Compensation & Commitment to Employee Performance in Pasar Mobil Kemayoran Management (PPMK). *Dinasti International Journal of Education Management And Social Science*, 1(6), 856-866.
- [20.] Jaya, K. Y. P., & Adnyani, I. G. A. D. (2015). Pengaruh gaya kepemimpinan terhadap disiplin kerja pegawai di Dinas Balai Bahasa Provinsi Bali (Doctoral dissertation, Udayana University).
- [21.] Kartika, L. N., & Sugiarto, A. (2014). Pengaruh Tingkat Kompetensi terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Administrasi Perkantoran. *Jurnal Ekonomi dan Bisnis*, 17(1), 73-90.
- [22.] Kasmir. (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori dan Praktik)*. Depok: PT. Rajagrafindo Persada.
- [23.] Kelimeda, K., Hairudinor, H., Ridwan, M. N. I., & Dalle, J. (2018). The Effect of Motivation, Job Satisfaction and Job Discipline toward Employee Performance of PT. Buma Perindahindo at lng Tangguh Site, Teluk Bintuni Regency, West Papua, Indonesia. *European Journal of Human Resource Management Studies*, 2 (1), 49-73.
- [24.] Kessler, Robin. (2011). *Competency Based Performance Reviews (terjemahan bahasa Indonesia)*. Jakarta: PPM.
- [25.] Mangkunegara, A.A Anwar Prabu. (2012). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
- [26.] Manullang, M. (2015). *Dasar-dasar Manajemen*. Yogyakarta: Gadjah Mada University Press.
- [27.] Meilany, P., & Ibrahim, M. (2015). Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja terhadap Kinerja Karyawan (Kasus Bagian Operasional PT. Indah Logistik Cargo, Cabang Pekanbaru). *Jom Fisip*, 2(2), 1-11.
- [28.] Ndolu, L., Niha, S. S., & Manafe, H. A. (2022). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional dan Budaya Organisasi terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Melalui Disiplin Kerja sebagai Variabel Mediasi (Suatu Kajian Studi Literatur Manajemen Sumberdaya Manusia). *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Sistem Informasi*, 4(2), 183-197.
- [29.] Nguyen, P. T., Yandi, A., & Mahaputra, M. R. (2020). Factors that influence employee performance: motivation, leadership, environment, culture organization, work achievement, competence and compensation (A study of human resource management literature studies). *Dinasti International Journal of Digital Business Management*, 1(4), 645-662.
- [30.] Paais, M., & Pattiruhu, J. R. (2020). Effect of Motivation, Leadership, and Organizational Culture on Satisfaction and Employee Performance. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(8), 577-588.
- [31.] Parashakti, R. D., Fahlevi, M., Ekhsan, M., & Hadinata, A. (2020, April). The Influence of Work Environment and Competence on Motivation and Its Impact on Employee Performance in Health Sector. In 3rd Asia Pacific International Conference of Management and Business Science (AICMBS 2019) (pp. 259-267). Atlantis Press.
- [32.] Pawirosumarto, S., Sarjana, P. K., & Gunawan, R. (2017). The Effect of Work Environment, Leadership Style, and Organizational Culture towards Job Satisfaction and Its Implication towards Employee Performance in Parador Hotels and Resorts, Indonesia. *International journal of law and management*. 59(6). 1337-1358.
- [33.] Peraturan Menteri Pendayagunaan Aparatur Negara dan Reformasi Birokrasi Nomor 8 Tahun 2021 tentang Sistem Manajemen Kinerja Pegawai Negeri Sipil.
- [34.] Rapika, R. & Sulaiman, S. (2020). Pengaruh Kompetensi Kerja terhadap Kinerja Pegawai dimana Disiplin dan Motivasi Kerja sebagai Variabel Mediasi pada Dinas Keuangan Kabupaten Gayo Lues. *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Gayo Lues*, 1(1), 203-210.
- [35.] Rivai, Veithzal. (2011). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia untuk Perusahaan*. Jakarta: Rajagrafindo Persada.
- [36.] Rostina, C. F., Siahaan, A. R. P., Fahtin, F., Harefa, T., & Gea, T. M. (2020). Influence of Leadership Style, Competence, and Work Discipline on Employee Performance in Pt. Sumo Internusa Indonesia. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (BIRCI-Journal): Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(3), 1961-1972.
- [37.] S., St. Sukmawati, & Alam, R. (2019). Pengaruh Motivasi, Kepemimpinan, dan Kompetensi terhadap Kinerja Pegawai pada Kantor Bappeda Kota Makassar. *MBIA*, 18(2), 172-181.
- [38.] Sastrohadiwiryo, Bejo Siswanto. (2013). *Manajemen Tenaga Kerja Indonesia: Pendekatan Administratif dan Operasional Edisi Revisi*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- [39.] Schermerhorn Jr, John R. (2011). *Introduction to Management (11th ed.)*, International Student Version. John Wiley & Sons.

- [40.] Sedarmayanti. (2017). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, Reformasi Birokrasi dan Manajemen Pegawai Negeri Sipil*. Bandung: Refika Aditama.
- [41.] Sekaran, U. and Bougie, R. (2016). *Research Methods for Business: A Skill-Building Approach*, 7th Edition. Wiley & Sons.
- [42.] Setiadi, M. T., & Lutfi, L. (2021). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional dan Komitmen Organisasi terhadap Kinerja Pegawai melalui Disiplin Kerja sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi pada Dinas Pekerjaan Umum dan Penataan Ruang Provinsi Banten). *Jurnal Riset Bisnis dan Manajemen Tirtayasa*, 5(2), 200-217.
- [43.] Sobariah, I., Sanusi, F., & Yazid, H. (2018). Strategi Meningkatkan Kinerja Pegawai dengan Disiplin Kerja sebagai Variabel Intervening di Kantor Kementerian Agama Kota Serang. *Jurnal Riset Bisnis dan Manajemen Tirtayasa*, 2(1), 97-112.
- [44.] Spencer, Lyle & Spencer, Signe M. (1993). *Competence at Work, Models for Superior Performance*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [45.] Sugiarto. (2017). *Metodologi Penelitian Bisnis*. Yogyakarta: Andi.
- [46.] Sugiyono. (2016). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R&D*. Bandung: PT Alfabet.
- [47.] Sujana, M. D. (2020). Pengaruh Kompensasi dan Kompetensi terhadap Kinerja Pegawai dengan Disiplin Kerja sebagai Variabel Intervening pada Dinas Prindustrian Kota Palembang. Doctoral Dissertation, Universitas Tridinanti.
- [48.] Sutrisno, Edy. (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Cetakan Kedelapan. Jakarta: Prenadamedia Group.
- [49.] Suyukoh, H., Mz, Masydzulhak Djamil., & Saluy, Ahmad Badawi. (2021). Effect of Work Motivation and Work Discipline on Performance of Bureau of Human Resources of The Polda Metro Jaya Employees with Work Environment as Intervening Variable. *Dinasti International Journal of Digital Business Management*, 2(4), 651-666.
- [50.] Tintami, L., Pradhanawati, A., & Nugraha, H. S. (2013). Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi dan Gaya Kepemimpinan Transformasional terhadap Kinerja Karyawan melalui Disiplin Kerja pada Harian SKT Megawon II PT. Jarum Kudus. *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Bisnis*, 1(1), 189-196.
- [51.] Turay, A. K., Salamah, S., & Riani, A. L. (2019). The Effect of Leadership Style, Self-Efficacy and Employee Training on Employee Performance at the Sierra Leone Airport Authority. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 6(2), 760-769.
- [52.] Wibowo. (2017). *Manajemen Kinerja Edisi 5*. Depok: Rajagrafindo Persada.
- [53.] Widodo, A.B., Mz, Masydzulhak Djamil., & Saluy, Ahmad Badawi. (2021). Effect of Work Environment and Work Competency on Performance of KPPU Employees with Work Discipline as Intervening Variable. *Dinasti International Journal of Digital Business Management*, 2(5), 872-897.
- [54.] Yukl, Gary. (2015). *Kepemimpinan Dalam Organisasi (Edisi 7)*. Jakarta : Indeks.
- [55.] Zikmund, W. G., Babin, B. J., Carr, J. C., & Griffin, M. (2013). *Business. Research Methods (International: 9th ed.)*. Canada : Cengage Learning.